

A NOTE ON THE ALKALOIDS OF *RAUWOLFIA SERPENTINA*, BENTH.

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The investigation of the alkaloidal constituents of the *Rauwolfia Serpentina* roots, collected from the Bihar province, had led to the isolation of a series of new alkaloids, namely ajmaline, $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$ (m.p. $158-60^\circ$), ajmalinine, $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$ (m.p. 181°), and ajmalicine (m.p. 252°) which are white crystalline bases and serpentine, $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ (m.p. 158°) and serpentinine, $C_{20}H_{26}O_5N_2$ (m.p. 265°) which are bright yellow crystalline products. The mutual relationship of four of these alkaloids has been fully discussed (Siddiqui and Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 10, 37 and preceding papers).

Since then further work on the constitution of these alkaloids had to be postponed owing to the difficulty of obtaining fresh air-dried roots and extremely poor yields of the bases from carelessly collected and stocked samples of the drug. Recently the author made a systematic study of the alkaloidal constituents of the roots and root-bark obtained from the Dun valley.

The detailed results of this investigation will be communicated later. In the present note it is merely intended to report that the constituents of the Dun drug are allied to the ajmaline series but are different in yield and character from alkaloids isolated from the Bihar variety. Thus, no ajmaline could be isolated from the crystalline hydrochloride fraction, and only traces of ajmalinine and serpentinine were found in one of the samples. On the other hand, isoajmaline (m.p. $264-66^\circ$) and an apparently new isomer, which has been provisionally named neoajmaline, (m.p. $205-7^\circ$), and which can be converted on heating at 270° or with alcoholic potash, into isoajmaline, were isolated from the crystalline hydrochloride, in 0.1 and 1% yields respectively from the root-bark and 0.01% and 0.1% yields from the whole roots. Another new alkaloid of this group melting at 220° has also been isolated from the root-bark and whole roots (yield about 0.02%) out of the alcohol-insoluble fraction of the base obtained from the mother-liquors of the crystalline hydrochloride. Further, from the neutral fraction of the alcoholic extract, a white crystalline alkaloid of amphoteric character melting at 234° was isolated in a yield of 0.1%.

Altogether the Dehradun variety contains very little of the yellow group of bases which are obviously oxidation products of the white ajmaline group. It is thus seen that the yellow oxidation bases of the plant growing in the hot swampy districts of Bihar are not formed in the milder climatic conditions of the Dun valley. It is interesting to note this from the point of view of the genetic connection between the two groups of bases in the plant body and the possibility of controlling the yield of one or the other of these groups by regional choice for the growth of the plant. The therapeutic importance, which the ajmaline group of alkaloids has gained, as a valuable hypnotic and general sedative for nervous complaints and for their curative properties in certain types of mental disorder, lends special significance to the findings reported in this note.

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